

ON THE ASYMPTOTIC FORMULA FOR THE GCD-SUM FUNCTION

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Abstract

For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we define the gcd-sum function $P(n) := \sum_{k=1}^n \gcd(k, n)$. We study the discrete higher moments of the function $A(n) = \frac{P(n)}{n}$ in the paper and obtain asymptotic formulae for the sums $\sum_{n \leq x} A^k(n)$ with improved error term for certain integers k .

1. Introduction

In 1933, Pillai [16] introduced the gcd-sum function

$$P(n) := \sum_{k=1}^n \gcd(k, n) = n \sum_{d|n} \frac{\varphi(d)}{d},$$

where φ is Euler's function. This arithmetical function is studied by many authors (see [1], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [10], [17], [18], [19]). Define $A(n) := \frac{P(n)}{n}$ for any integer $n \geq 1$. In 2010, Tóth [18] considered the summatory function $\sum_{n \leq x} A^2(n)$ and established the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^2(n) = xP_3(\log x) + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}+\epsilon}),$$

where $P_3(\log x)$ is a polynomial of degree 3 in $\log x$.

Later, in 2013, Zhang and Zhai [19] gave an asymptotic formula for the summatory function $\sum_{n \leq x} A^k(n)$ for any integer $k \geq 2$, which is

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^k(n) = xQ^{2^k-1}(\log x) + O(x^{\beta_k+\epsilon}), \tag{1}$$

(For $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, $Q_\ell(y)$ denotes a polynomial of degree ℓ in y). The β_k 's in the error term are given by

$$\beta_2 = \frac{1}{2}, \beta_3 = \frac{5}{8}, \beta_4 = \frac{7}{9}, \beta_5 = \frac{31}{36}, \beta_6 = \frac{207}{224}, \text{ and } \beta_k = 1 - \frac{1}{50.2^{\frac{2}{3}k}} \text{ for } k \geq 7.$$

It is not difficult to see that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} A(n) &= \sum_{n \leq x} \sum_{d|n} \frac{\varphi(d)}{d} = \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\varphi(d)}{d} \sum_{q \leq \frac{x}{d}} 1 \\ &= \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\varphi(d)}{d} \left\{ \frac{x}{d} + O(1) \right\} \\ &= x \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\varphi(d)}{d^2} + O\left(\sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\varphi(d)}{d} \right) \\ &= cx \log x + O(x). \end{aligned}$$

Throughout the paper, C_1, C_2, \dots with or without suffixes, denote effective positive constants and may depend only on k , and need not be the same at each occurrence. Similarly, the number ϵ is any small positive constant, the value of which need not be the same in different occurrences. The aim of this paper is to improve the error term in 1 for $k = 2, k = 3$, and $7 \leq k \leq 11$. Indeed, we prove the following theorems.

Theorem 1. *For $k = 2$ and $x \geq x_0$, where x_0 is sufficiently large, we have*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^2(n) = M_2(x) + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(C_2(\log \log x)^2)).$$

Theorem 2. *For $k = 3$ and $x \geq x_0$, where x_0 is sufficiently large, we have*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^3(n) = M_3(x) + O(x^{\frac{5}{8}} \exp(C_3(\log \log x)^2)).$$

Theorem 3. *For $k = 4$ and $x \geq x_0$, where x_0 is sufficiently large, we have*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^4(n) = M_4(x) + O(x^{\frac{157}{199}+\epsilon}).$$

Theorem 4. *Let $k \geq 5$ be any fixed integer and $x \geq x_0$, where x_0 is sufficiently large, we have*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^k(n) = M_k(x) + O_k(x^{1+2\epsilon - \frac{42}{13 \cdot 2^k - 9}}).$$

Remark 1. Clearly, the exponents of the error terms appearing in Theorems 1 and 2 are improvements of the exponents β_2, β_3 (appearing in (1)), respectively. We also notice that $1 - \frac{42}{13(2^k) - 9} < 1 - \frac{1}{50(2^{\frac{2}{3}k})}$, provided $\frac{1}{50(2^{\frac{2}{3}k})} < \frac{42}{13(2^k) - 9}$. It is enough to secure the inequality $13(2^k) - 9 < 13(2^k) < 2100(2^{\frac{2}{3}k})$ (i.e., $2^{\frac{k}{3}} \leq \frac{2100}{13}$). By taking the logarithm, we see that, Theorem 4 is an improvement as long as $7 \leq k \leq 22$. Note that $k \leq \left\lfloor \frac{3 \log(\frac{2100}{13})}{\log 2} \right\rfloor = 22$. It should be noted that in Theorem 3, the exponent of the error term is $\frac{157}{199} = 0.7889 > \beta_4 = \frac{7}{9} = 0.7777\dots$

2. Preliminaries and Some Lemmas

To establish our main theorems, we need the following lemmas.

Lemma 1 ([11], Theorem 8.4 and 8.8). *For any $\epsilon > 0$, we have*

$$\int_0^T \left| \zeta\left(\frac{5}{7} + it\right) \right|^{12} dt \ll_{\epsilon} T^{1+\epsilon},$$

uniformly for $T \geq 1$.

Lemma 2 ([9]). *For T sufficiently large, we have*

$$\int_{\frac{T}{2}}^T \left| \zeta\left(\frac{5}{8} + it\right) \right|^8 dt \ll T(\log T)^{38},$$

uniformly.

Lemma 3 ([12]). *For any $\epsilon > 0$, we have*

$$\int_1^T |\zeta(\sigma + it)|^{12} dt = T \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_6^2(n)}{n^{2\sigma}} + O(T^{\frac{9-7\sigma}{4} + \epsilon}),$$

for any fixed σ satisfying $\frac{5}{7} < \sigma < 1$ and $|t| \geq 1$.

Lemma 4 ([9]). *For T sufficiently large, we have*

$$\int_1^T \left| \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^{12} dt \ll T^2(\log T)^{17},$$

uniformly.

Lemma 5 ([13]). *For T sufficiently large, we have*

$$\int_{10}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{1}{2} + it)|^4}{|\zeta(1 + 2it)|} dt \ll T(\log T)^5,$$

uniformly.

Lemma 6 ([14], [2]). *For any $\epsilon > 0$, we have*

$$\zeta(\sigma + it) \ll_{\epsilon} (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{13}{42}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \epsilon},$$

uniformly for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1 + \epsilon$ and $|t| \geq 1$.

Lemma 7 ([15]). *For $U \geq U_0$, where U_0 is sufficiently large, there exists a point $T^* \in (U, 2U)$ such that*

$$\max_{\sigma \geq \frac{1}{2}} |\zeta(\sigma \pm iT^*)| \leq \exp(C(\log \log U)^2) \ll U^{\epsilon}.$$

Lemma 8 ([10]). *Let s be a complex variable with $\Re(s) > 1$. Then we have*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A^k(n)}{n^s} = \zeta^{2^k}(s) G_k(s),$$

where $G_k(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{g(n)}{n^s}$ is a Dirichlet series which is absolutely convergent for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$. Moreover, we have

$$G_k(s) = \frac{\tilde{G}_{k,2}(s)}{\zeta^{4^k - 3^k - \binom{2^k}{2}}(2s)}, \tag{2}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{G}_{k,2}(s) = & \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{2s}} \right)^{3^k - 4^k + \binom{2^k}{2}} \left(1 + \frac{3^k - 4^k + \binom{2^k}{2}}{p^{2s}} - \frac{k2^{k-1}}{p^{s+1}} + \dots + (-1)^k \frac{1}{p^{s+k}} \right. \\ & + \frac{4^k - 6^k + \binom{2^k}{2} 2^k - \binom{2^k}{3}}{p^{3s}} + \frac{k2^{k-1} - 2k3^{k-1}}{p^{2s+1}} + \dots \\ & \left. + \frac{2k \cdot 2^k 3^{k-1} - 3k \cdot 4^{k-1} - k \cdot 2^{k-1} \binom{2^k}{2}}{p^{3s+1}} + \dots \right), \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

which is absolutely convergent for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{3}$.

Now we discuss the structure of the L -function $G_k(s)$.

3. Structure of L -function $G_k(s)$

Let

$$F_k(s) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A^k(n)}{n^s}.$$

For $k \geq 2$, by Lemma 8, we can express $F_k(s)$ as

$$F_k(s) = \frac{\zeta^{2^k}(s)}{\zeta^{4^k-3^k-\binom{2^k}{2}}(2s)} \tilde{G}_{k,2}(s).$$

By [10], $\tilde{G}_{k,2}(s)$ absolutely converges in the half-plane $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{3}$. From Equation (2), we have

$$G_k(s) = \frac{\tilde{G}_{k,2}(s)}{\zeta^{4^k-3^k-\binom{2^k}{2}}(2s)}.$$

By induction, we can express $G_k(s)$ as

$$G_k(s) = \frac{\tilde{G}_{k,n}(s)}{\zeta^{4^k-3^k-\binom{2^k}{2}}(2s)\zeta^{\ell_3}(3s)\zeta^{\ell_4}(4s)\cdots\zeta^{\ell_n}(ns)}.$$

From Equation (3), we see that

$$\ell_m = \sum_{r=0}^{2^k} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} ((m+1)-r)^k \quad 2 \leq m \leq n.$$

Theorem 5. *For any fixed integer $k \geq 2$, $\ell_m = 0$ for $m \geq 2^k - 1$. Therefore, $\tilde{G}_{k,n}(s)$ converges absolutely for $\sigma > \frac{1}{n}$ for any fixed $k \geq 2$. In particular, for $k = 2$ we have*

$$F_2(s) = \frac{\zeta^4(s)}{\zeta(2s)} \tilde{G}_{2,2}(s),$$

where $\tilde{G}_{2,2}(s)$ is a Dirichlet series that converges absolutely in the half-plane $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{n}$ for any positive integer n .

In order to prove the theorem stated above, we first require the following lemmas. Similar results related to this lemma can be found in [8, Sec. 1.6].

Lemma 9. *Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 \leq \ell < n$. Then*

$$\sum_{r=0}^n (-1)^r \binom{n}{r} r^\ell = 0.$$

Proof. Let

$$f(x) = (1 - x)^n = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} (-x)^r.$$

By taking $x = 1$, we have $\sum_{r=0}^n (-1)^r \binom{n}{r} = 0$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x) &:= x \frac{df}{dx} = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} (-x)^r r, \\ f_2(x) &:= x \frac{df_1}{dx} = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} (-x)^r r^2, \\ &\vdots \\ f_i(x) &:= x \frac{df_{i-1}}{dx} = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} (-x)^r r^i. \end{aligned}$$

For each $i \leq n - 1$, $(1 - x)$ divides $x \frac{df_i}{dx}$, and hence $f_i(1) = 0$ for all $i \leq n - 1$. Therefore, we have

$$\sum_{r=0}^n (-1)^r \binom{n}{r} r^\ell = 0, \quad \text{for all } \ell < n.$$

□

Corollary 1. *Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 \leq \ell < n$. Then*

$$\sum_{r=0}^n (-1)^r \binom{n}{r} (r - 1)^\ell = 0.$$

Proof. Since $(r - 1)^\ell$ is a polynomial of degree ℓ in r , using Lemma 9 we obtain

$$\sum_{r=0}^n (-1)^r \binom{n}{r} (r - 1)^\ell = 0.$$

□

Proof of Theorem 5. First, we consider the case $n = 2^k - 1$. In this case, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r=0}^{2^k-1} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} (2^k - r)^k &= \sum_{r=0}^{2^k-1} \left[(-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} \left(\sum_{l=0}^k \binom{k}{l} (-1)^l (2^k)^{k-l} r^l \right) \right] \\ &= \sum_{l=0}^k \left[(-1)^l (2^k)^{k-l} \binom{k}{l} \left(\sum_{r=0}^{2^k-1} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} r^l \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

By Lemma 9, we have

$$\sum_{r=0}^{2^k} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} r^l = 0.$$

Separating the last term, we obtain

$$\sum_{r=0}^{2^k-1} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} r^l = -(2^k)^l.$$

Using this relation in Equation (4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r=0}^{2^k-1} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} (2^k - r)^k &= \sum_{l=0}^k (-1)^l (2^k)^{k-l} \binom{k}{l} \times -(2^k)^l \\ &= -(2^k)^k \sum_{l=0}^k (-1)^l \binom{k}{l} \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Now, when $n \geq 2^k$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r=0}^{2^k} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} ((n+1) - r)^k &= \sum_{r=0}^{2^k} \left[(-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} \left(\sum_{l=0}^k \binom{k}{l} (-1)^l n^{k-l} (r-1)^l \right) \right] \\ &= \sum_{l=0}^k \left[(-1)^l n^{k-l} \binom{k}{l} \left(\sum_{r=0}^{2^k} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} (r-1)^l \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

By Corollary 1, we have

$$\sum_{r=0}^{2^k} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} (r-1)^l = 0.$$

Using this identity in Equation (5), we get

$$\sum_{r=0}^{2^k} (-1)^r \binom{2^k}{r} ((n+1) - r)^k = 0.$$

Hence, $\ell_n = 0$ for all $n \geq 2^k - 1$. □

4. Proof of the Main Theorems

Proof of Theorem 1. We choose $T = \pm T_1^* \in (U, 2U)$ such that Lemma 7 is satisfied. Applying Perron’s formula to $F_2(s)$, we obtain

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^2(n) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right).$$

We move the line of integration to $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{2}$. Let R be the rectangle with the vertices $\frac{1}{2} \pm iT$ and $1 + \frac{1}{\log x} \pm iT$. In the rectangle R , the function $F_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ has a pole of multiplicity 4 at $s = 1$. Thus, by using Cauchy’s residue theorem on R , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds &= M_2(x) + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left\{ - \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT}^{\frac{1}{2}+iT} - \int_{\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{\frac{1}{2}+iT} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_{\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT} \right\} F_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds, \end{aligned}$$

where $M_2(x)$ is the main term, given by the residue of $F_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ at $s = 1$.

Now we begin by estimating the horizontal contribution $C_{H,2}$ along the line from $\frac{1}{2} + iT$ to $1 + \frac{1}{\log x} + iT$. We assume that $T \geq 10$, and it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,2}| &\ll \left| \int_{\frac{1}{2}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} \left| \frac{\zeta^4(s)}{\zeta(2s)} \tilde{G}_{2,2}(s) \frac{x^s}{s} \right| ds \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} \frac{|\zeta(s)|^4}{|\zeta(2s)|} |\tilde{G}_{2,2}(s)| \frac{|x^s|}{|s|} ds. \end{aligned}$$

For $\sigma > \frac{1}{2}$, $|\tilde{G}_{2,2}(s)|$ is bounded, and $\frac{1}{|\zeta(2s)|} \ll \log(|T| + 10)$. Moreover, by Lemma 7, for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1 + \frac{1}{\log x}$, we have

$$|\zeta(s)|^4 \ll \exp(C_2(\log \log T)^2).$$

Therefore,

$$|C_{H,2}| \ll (\log T) \cdot \exp(C_2(\log \log T)^2) \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}} \frac{|x^{\sigma+iT}|}{|\sigma+iT|} d\sigma,$$

from which it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,2}| &\ll (\log T) \cdot \exp(C_2(\log \log T)^2) \frac{x^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}}}{T} \\ &\ll \frac{xx^{\frac{1}{\log x}}}{T} \exp(C_2(\log \log T)^2) \\ &\ll \frac{x}{T} \exp(C_2(\log \log x)^2), \end{aligned}$$

since our choice of T is going to be a power of x .

Now we estimate the left vertical contribution $C_{V,2}$ of $F_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ in absolute value, that is,

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{V,2}| &\leq \left| \int_{\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{\frac{1}{2}+iT} F_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{\frac{1}{2}+iT} \frac{|\zeta(s)|^4 |x^s|}{|\zeta(2s)| |s|} ds \\ &\ll \int_{-T}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{1}{2}+it)|^4 x^{\frac{1}{2}}}{|\zeta(1+2it)| t} dt \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{2}} + x^{\frac{1}{2}} \int_{10}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{1}{2}+it)|^4}{|\zeta(1+2it)|} \frac{1}{t} dt. \end{aligned}$$

Using Lemma 5, we get

$$|C_{V,2}| \ll x^{\frac{1}{2}} + x^{\frac{1}{2}} (\log T)^5.$$

Therefore, the total contributions of $F_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ (i.e., the sum of the horizontal and vertical contribution and $O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right)$), is given by

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,2}| + |C_{V,2}| + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right) &\ll \frac{x}{T} \exp(C_2(\log \log x)^2) + x^{\frac{1}{2}} (\log T)^5 \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right). \end{aligned}$$

We choose $T = x^{\frac{1}{2}}$ to obtain an optimal estimate, so that

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,2}| + |C_{V,2}| + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right) &= O(x^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(C_2(\log \log x)^2)) + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}} (\log x^{\frac{1}{2}})^5) \\ &\quad + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}} (\log x)^2). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^2(n) = M_2(x) + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(C_2(\log \log x)^2)).$$

This proves Theorem 1. □

Proof of Theorem 2. We choose $T = \pm T_2^* \in (U, 2U)$ satisfying Lemma 7. By applying Perron's formula to $F_3(s)$, we get

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^3(n) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right).$$

Now, we shift the line of integration to $\Re(s) = \frac{5}{8}$. Let R be the rectangle with the vertices $\frac{5}{8} \pm iT$ and $1 + \frac{1}{\log x} \pm iT$. In the rectangle R , $F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ has a pole of multiplicity 8 at $s = 1$. Now, by using Cauchy's residue theorem on the rectangle R , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds &= M_3(x) + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left\{ - \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT}^{\frac{5}{8}+iT} - \int_{\frac{5}{8}+iT}^{\frac{5}{8}-iT} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_{\frac{5}{8}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT} \right\} F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds, \end{aligned}$$

where $M_3(x)$ is the main term (i.e., the residue of $F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$) at $s = 1$.

First, we estimate the horizontal contribution $C_{H,3}$ of $F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ (i.e., sum of the contributions of the line integrals $\int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT}^{\frac{5}{8}+iT} F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds$ and $\int_{\frac{5}{8}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT} F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds$ in absolute value) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,3}| &\ll \left| \int_{\frac{5}{8}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{5}{8}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} \left| \frac{\zeta^8(s)}{\zeta^9(2s)} \tilde{G}_{3,2}(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\leq \int_{\frac{5}{8}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} \frac{|\zeta(s)|^8}{|\zeta(2s)|^9} |\tilde{G}_{3,2}(s)| \frac{|x^s|}{|s|} ds. \end{aligned}$$

For $\sigma > \frac{5}{8}$, $|\tilde{G}_{3,2}(s)|$ and $\frac{1}{|\zeta(2s)|^9}$ are bounded, and hence

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,3}| &\ll \int_{\frac{5}{8}}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}} |\zeta(\sigma + iT)|^8 \frac{x^\sigma}{T} d\sigma \\ &\ll \frac{x^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}}}{T} \int_{\frac{5}{8}}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}} |\zeta(\sigma + iT)|^8 d\sigma. \end{aligned}$$

By using Lemma 7, we get

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,3}| &\ll \frac{x x^{\frac{1}{\log x}}}{T} \exp(C_3(\log \log T)^2) \\ &\ll \frac{x}{T} \exp(C_3(\log \log x)^2), \end{aligned}$$

as our choice of T is going to be a power of x .

Now we estimate the vertical contribution $C_{V,3}$ in absolute value, that is,

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{V,3}| &\leq \left| \int_{\frac{5}{8}-iT}^{\frac{5}{8}+iT} F_3(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{5}{8}-iT}^{\frac{5}{8}+iT} \frac{|\zeta(s)|^8}{|\zeta(2s)|^9} |\tilde{G}_{3,2}(s)| \frac{|x^s|}{|s|} ds \\ &\ll \int_{-T}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{8} + it)|^8}{|\zeta(\frac{5}{4} + 2it)|^9} |\tilde{G}_{3,2}(\frac{5}{8} + it)| \frac{|x^{\frac{5}{8}+it}|}{|\frac{5}{8} + it|} dt \\ &\ll x^{\frac{5}{8}} + x^{\frac{5}{8}} \int_{\frac{T}{2}}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{8} + it)|^8}{|\zeta(\frac{5}{4} + 2it)|^9} |\tilde{G}_{3,2}(\frac{5}{8} + iT)| \frac{1}{t} dt. \end{aligned}$$

As $\frac{5}{8} > \frac{1}{3}$, both $|\tilde{G}_{3,2}(\frac{5}{8} + iT)|$ and $\frac{1}{|\zeta(\frac{5}{4} + 2it)|^9}$ are bounded. Hence, we have

$$|C_{V,3}| \ll x^{\frac{5}{8}} + x^{\frac{5}{8}} \int_{\frac{T}{2}}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{8} + it)|^8}{t} dt.$$

By using Lemma 2 and partial integration, we obtain

$$|C_{V,3}| \ll x^{\frac{5}{8}} (\log x)^{39}.$$

Therefore, in total, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,3}| + |C_{V,3}| + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right) &\ll \frac{x}{T} \exp(C_3(\log \log x)^2) + x^{\frac{5}{8}} (\log x)^{39} \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right). \end{aligned}$$

To get an optimal estimate, we choose $T = x^{\frac{3}{8}}$, so that we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,3}| + |C_{V,3}| + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right) &= O(x^{\frac{5}{8}} \exp(C_3(\log \log x)^2)) \\ &\quad + O(x^{\frac{5}{8}} (\log x)^{39}) + O(x^{\frac{5}{8}} (\log x)^2). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^3(n) = M_3(x) + O(x^{\frac{5}{8}} \exp(C_3(\log \log x)^2)).$$

This proves Theorem 2. □

Proof of Theorem 3. As before, we choose $T = \pm T_3^* \in (U, 2U)$ satisfying Lemma 7.

By applying Perron's formula to $F_4(s)$, we get

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^4(n) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_4(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right).$$

Now we move the line of integration to $\Re(s) = \frac{5}{7}$. Let R be the rectangle with vertices $\frac{5}{7} \pm iT$ and $1 + \frac{1}{\log x} \pm iT$. We note that the function $F_4(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ has a pole of multiplicity 16 at $s = 1$. Thus, by using Cauchy's residue theorem on the rectangle R , we have

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_4(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds = M_4(x) + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left\{ - \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT}^{\frac{5}{7}+iT} - \int_{\frac{5}{7}+iT}^{\frac{5}{7}-iT} - \int_{\frac{5}{7}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT} \right\} F_4(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds,$$

where $M_4(x)$ is the main term (i.e., the residue of $F_4(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ at $s = 1$).

Now we estimate the horizontal contribution $C_{H,4}$ in absolute value:

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,4}| &\ll \left| \int_{\frac{5}{7}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_4(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\leq \int_{\frac{5}{7}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} \frac{|\zeta(s)|^{16}}{|\zeta(2s)|^{55}} |\tilde{G}_{4,2}(s)| \frac{|x^s|}{|s|} ds. \end{aligned}$$

We note that $|\tilde{G}_{4,2}(s)|$ and $\frac{1}{|\zeta(2s)|^{55}}$ are bounded for $\sigma \geq \frac{5}{7}$. Hence, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,4}| &\ll \int_{\frac{5}{7}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} |\zeta(s)|^{16} \frac{|x^s|}{|s|} ds \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{5}{7}}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}} |\zeta(\sigma + iT)|^{16} \frac{x^\sigma}{T} d\sigma \\ &\ll \frac{x x^{\frac{1}{\log x}}}{T} \int_{\frac{5}{7}}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}} |\zeta(\sigma + iT)|^{16} d\sigma. \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 7, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,4}| &\ll \frac{x x^{\frac{1}{\log x}}}{T} (\exp(C(\log \log T))^2)^{16} \\ &\ll \frac{x}{T} \exp(C_4(\log \log x)^2), \end{aligned}$$

as our choice of T is going to be a power of x .

The estimate of the vertical contribution $C_{V,4}$ in absolute value is given by

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{V,4}| &\leq \left| \int_{\frac{5}{7}-iT}^{\frac{5}{7}+iT} F_4(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\ll \left| \int_{\frac{5}{7}-iT}^{\frac{5}{7}+iT} \frac{\zeta^{16}(s)}{\zeta^{55}(2s)} \tilde{G}_{4,2}(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\ll \int_{-T}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{7} + it)|^{16}}{|\zeta(\frac{10}{7} + 2iT)|^{55}} |\tilde{G}_{4,2}(\frac{5}{7} + it)| \frac{|x^{\frac{5}{7}+it}|}{|\frac{5}{7} + it|} dt \\ &\ll \int_{-T}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{7} + it)|^{16}}{|\zeta(\frac{10}{7} + 2iT)|^{55}} |\tilde{G}_{4,2}(\frac{5}{7} + it)| \frac{x^{\frac{5}{7}}}{t} dt. \end{aligned}$$

As $|\tilde{G}_{4,2}(\frac{5}{7} + it)|$ and $\frac{1}{|\zeta(2s)|^{55}}$ are bounded for $\sigma > \frac{1}{3}$ and for $t \in \mathbb{R}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{V,4}| &\ll \int_{-T}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{7} + it)|^{16}}{t} x^{\frac{5}{7}} dt \\ &\ll x^{\frac{5}{7}} + x^{\frac{5}{7}} \int_0^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{7} + it)|^{16}}{t} dt \\ &\leq x^{\frac{5}{7}} + x^{\frac{5}{7}} \int_0^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{7} + it)|^{12}}{t} |\zeta(\frac{5}{7} + it)|^4 dt, \quad |T| \geq 1. \end{aligned}$$

By using Lemmas 1 and 6, together with partial integration, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{V,4}| &\ll x^{\frac{5}{7}} (1 + T)^{\frac{52}{147} + \epsilon} \int_0^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{7} + it)|^{12}}{t} dt \\ &\ll_{\epsilon} x^{\frac{5}{7}} T^{\frac{52}{147} + 2\epsilon}. \end{aligned}$$

The total contribution is given by

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,4}| + |C_{V,4}| + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right) &\ll \frac{x}{T} \exp(C_4(\log \log x)^2) + x^{\frac{5}{7}} T^{\frac{52}{147} + 2\epsilon} \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right). \end{aligned}$$

To get an optimal value, we choose $T = x^{\frac{42}{199}}$ so that

$$|C_{H,4}| + |C_{V,4}| + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right) \ll x^{\frac{157}{199} + 2\epsilon}.$$

Hence,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^4(n) = M_4(x) + O(x^{\frac{157}{199} + 2\epsilon}).$$

This proves Theorem 3. □

Proof of Theorem 4. Again, our choice of $T = \pm T_4^* \in (U, 2U)$ satisfies Lemma 7. By applying Perron’s formula to $F_k(s)$, we get

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^k(n) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_k(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right).$$

Now we shift the line of integration to $\Re(s) = \frac{5}{7}$. Let R be the rectangle with vertices $\frac{5}{7} \pm iT$ and $1 + \frac{1}{\log x} \pm iT$. In R , $F_k(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$ has a pole of multiplicity 2^k at $s = 1$. Now, by applying Cauchy’s residue theorem on the rectangle R , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_k(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds &= M_k(x) + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left\{ - \int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT}^{\frac{5}{7}+iT} - \int_{\frac{5}{7}+iT}^{\frac{5}{7}-iT} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_{\frac{5}{7}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT} \right\} F_k(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds, \end{aligned}$$

where $M_k(x)$ is the main term (i.e., $\text{Res}(F_k(s) \frac{x^s}{s})$ at $s = 1$).

First, we calculate the horizontal contribution $C_{H,k}$, which is given by the line integrals $\int_{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT}^{\frac{5}{7}+iT} F_k(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds$ and $\int_{\frac{5}{7}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}-iT} F_k(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,k}| &\ll \left| \int_{\frac{5}{7}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} F_k(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{5}{7}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} \left| \frac{\zeta^{2^k}(s)}{\zeta^{4^k-3^k-\binom{2^k}{2}}(2s)} \tilde{G}_{k,2}(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{5}{7}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}+iT} \frac{|\zeta(s)|^{2^k}}{|\zeta(2s)|^{4^k-3^k-\binom{2^k}{2}}} |\tilde{G}_{k,2}(s)| \frac{|x^s|}{|s|} ds. \end{aligned}$$

Since $|\tilde{G}_k(s)|$ and $|\zeta(2s)|^{4^k-3^k-\binom{2^k}{2}}$ are bounded for any $\sigma \geq \frac{5}{7}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,k}| &\ll \int_{\frac{5}{7}}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}} |\zeta(\sigma+iT)|^{2^k} \frac{|x^{\sigma+iT}|}{|\sigma+iT|} d\sigma \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{5}{7}}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}} |\zeta(\sigma+iT)|^{2^k} \frac{x^\sigma}{T} \\ &\ll \frac{x x^{\frac{1}{\log x}}}{T} \int_{\frac{5}{7}}^{1+\frac{1}{\log x}} |\zeta(\sigma+iT)|^{2^k} d\sigma. \end{aligned}$$

By using Lemma 7, for sufficiently large T , we have

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,k}| &\ll \frac{x x^{\frac{1}{\log x}}}{T} \exp(2^k C (\log \log T)^2) \\ &\ll \frac{x}{T} \exp(C_k (\log \log x)^2), \end{aligned}$$

where C_k is an effective positive constant depending on k , since our choice of T is going to be a power of x .

The contribution of the left vertical line in absolute value is given by

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{V,k}| &\leq \left| \int_{\frac{5}{7}-iT}^{\frac{5}{7}+iT} F_k(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| \\ &\leq \int_{\frac{5}{7}-iT}^{\frac{5}{7}+iT} \left| \frac{\zeta^{2^k}(s)}{\zeta^{4^k-3^k-\binom{2^k}{2}}(2s)} \tilde{G}_{k,2}(s) \frac{x^s}{s} \right| ds \\ &\ll \int_{-T}^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{7}+it)|^{2^k}}{|\zeta(\frac{10}{7}+2it)|^{4^k-3^k-\binom{2^k}{2}}} |\tilde{G}_{k,2}(\frac{5}{7}+it)| \frac{|x^{\frac{5}{7}+it}|}{|\frac{5}{7}+it|} dt. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $|\tilde{G}_{k,2}(\frac{5}{7}+it)|$ and $|\zeta(\frac{10}{7}+2it)|^{4^k-3^k-\binom{2^k}{2}}$ are convergent for all $\sigma > \frac{5}{7}$. Thus, we have

$$|C_{V,k}| \ll x^{\frac{5}{7}} + x^{\frac{5}{7}} \int_0^T \frac{|\zeta(\frac{5}{7}+it)|^{12}}{t} |\zeta(\frac{5}{7}+it)|^{2^k-12} dt.$$

By using Lemmas 1 and 6, along with partial integration, we get

$$|C_{V,k}| \ll x^{\frac{5}{7}} + x^{\frac{5}{7}} T^{\frac{13}{147}(2^k-12)+2\epsilon}.$$

Therefore, in total we have

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,k}| + |C_{V,K}| + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right) &\ll \frac{x}{T} \exp(C_k(\log \log x)^2) \\ &\quad + x^{\frac{5}{7}} T^{\frac{13}{147}(2^k-12)+2\epsilon} + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right). \end{aligned}$$

To get an optimal value, we choose $T = x^{\frac{42}{13 \cdot 2^k - 9}}$, so that

$$\begin{aligned} |C_{H,k}| + |C_{V,K}| + O\left(\frac{x(\log x)^2}{T}\right) &= O\left(x^{(1-\frac{42}{13 \cdot 2^k - 9})} \exp(2^k C(\log \log x)^2)\right) \\ &\quad + O\left(x^{(1-\frac{42}{13 \cdot 2^k - 9}+2\epsilon)}\right) + O\left(x^{(1-\frac{42}{13 \cdot 2^k - 9})} (\log x)^2\right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^k(n) = M_k(x) + O_k\left(x^{1+2\epsilon-\frac{42}{13 \cdot 2^k - 9}}\right).$$

This proves Theorem 4. □

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